

Minutes of the 46th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Tuesday 15th February 2011
(This document was finalised on 1st July 2011)

Present:

Ms Judith Agnew¹ (JLA)
Dr Bogdan Antonescu²
Dr Catherine Gaffard³ (CG)
Dr David Hooper^{1,4} (DAH) Secretary
Mr Dan Housley² (DJH)
Dr Dirk Klugmann³ (DK)
Mr Chris Lee² (CFL)
Mr Jesse Norris²
Dr Emily Norton² (EGN)
Dr Graham Parton^{1,5} (GAP)
Dr Jeremy Price³ (JP)
Prof Geraint Vaughan² (GV) Chair
Mr Charles Wrench^{1,4}

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⁴NERC MST Radar Facility

⁵British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BL(WP) Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
DPW Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
FGAM (NERC) Facility for Ground-based Atmospheric Measurement (formerly UFAM)
GNNS Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS Global Positioning System
LCBR Laser Cloud Base Recorder
LD Les Dean (part-time MSTRF site technician)
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS (NERC) National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
PAT Portable Appliance Testing
PC Personal Computer
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

It was stated in Section 5a that a dedicated clutter screen was built around the entire FGAM boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP), not just around the central panel. This should have referred to the Met Office's BLWP at Chilbolton.

It was stated, in the 4th paragraph of section 6a, that unexpectedly and controversially large mean val-

ues of the lidar ratio had been derived for the April period. GV clarified that although this had been correctly reported in the minutes, a re-analysis of the data had shown the original values to have been overestimated.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 44.4.2 DAH and GAP to ensure that different versions of MST radar data products stored on the BADC are clearly distinguishable and that no old versions are deleted when the reprocessing of the entire observation archive is undertaken.

ONGOING

No new versions of MST radar data files have so far been produced and so this action item has not yet come into effect.

ACTION ITEM 45.5.1 HMAR to include details of the UofM lidar observations of volcanic ash on the CEDA website as soon as possible.

COMPLETED

GV reported that grant money had been obtained for the volcanic ash work and so papers would ultimately follow.

3. Facility Report

3a) MST Radar renovation

A major renovation of the MST radar is due to take place between Monday 28th February and Wednesday 16th March 2011. Although it is likely that test observations will begin towards the end of the period, the radar should be considered to be out of action for the duration. No data will be sent to the Met Office until it is clear that the renovated radar is operating as expected.

The focus of the work is on replacing the beam steering components. The existing phasing units have been repeatedly reconditioned, rather than being replaced, and have now reached the end of their useful working lives. The combination of the new phasing units and the new beam steering controller will allow the number of available beam pointing directions to increase from 16 to 256.

In order to provide a benchmark dataset for evaluating the performance of the renovated radar, a special observation format was introduced on 9th February 2011. This encompasses all 16 of the currently-available beam pointing directions; only 6 of these are used for standard observations. The special observation format will continue to be used until the renovation work begins. A slightly modified version will be implemented for a few weeks afterwards.

The introduction of the special observation format was deliberately timed so that it could serve an additional purpose. Members of RAL staff visited the Aberystwyth area on 10th and 11th February 2011 in order to evaluate potential sites for a secondary UK LOFAR (LOW Frequency ARray) receiving station. The aim of the LOFAR project - see <http://www.lofar-uk.org/> - is to make radio-astronomical observations in the poorly-explored 30-240 MHz band. There are already a number of receiving stations spread across Europe, including one at Chilbolton. The high-powered 46.5 MHz MST radar transmissions clearly have the potential to obscure part of the LOFAR spectrum for any receiving station which is located nearby. However, it is not yet clear whether direct transmissions through radar sidelobes, reflections from topographic features, or backscatter from the atmosphere might pose the biggest problem. Making use of all available beam pointing directions therefore allowed the tests to be carried out as fully

as possible. Analysis of the test data is currently being undertaken.

3b) Electricity - including NERC's Voltage Optimisation scheme

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units have indicated 13 instances of brief fluctuations in the mains electricity supply over the past 6 months: on 3rd July 2010, 20th and 22nd August, 8th September, 2nd November 2010 (on 3 separate occasions), 11th, 12th, 19th and 26th January 2011, and on 5th February (on 2 separate occasions). None of these will have affected any of the equipment supplied by the UPS units.

The electricity supply for the whole Capel Dewi area was down between approximately 08:00 and 14:00 UT on 2nd August 2010. This was to allow scheduled maintenance work to be carried out on the local distribution network. All pieces of equipment at the site were powered down in a controlled manner before 08:00 UT and then restarted after the electricity supply was resumed. Only the Campbell Scientific data-loggers continued to operate during this period.

Each piece of equipment was powered down for a short period on the morning of 1st December 2010. This was to allow Portable Appliance Testing (PAT) to be carried out on the mains cables.

NERC is in the process of carrying out "voltage optimisation" at all of its sites. This is an attempt both to save money and to reduce its carbon footprint. It is based on the principle that many (but not all) items of electrical and electronic equipment will reduce their power consumption if operated at voltages of around 220 V rather than 240 V. Savings of around 10% have been predicted for a number of NERC sites. However, more-modest savings are anticipated for the MST radar site owing to the types of equipment operated there. Voltage optimisation is achieved by installing a specialised step-down transformer in-line with a site's main electricity supply. A unit manufactured by powerPerfactor was due to be installed at the MST radar site on the day of this Experimenters' meeting (i.e. 15th February 2011). Consequently all equipment had been powered down by Les Dean (LD) at around 09:30 UT and was due to be restarted later in the day. On the previous day (i.e. 14th February), Dave Wareing (DPW) had drawn attention to the fact that there are actually two electricity supplies from the main distribution board (in the wooden shed) to the site bungalow. powerPerfactor do not appear to have realised this but have now been made aware of the fact. If voltage optimisation is carried out at the point in the circuit which they initially recommended, it will only affect the supply to the transmitter room.

DAH pointed out that all modern items of equipment, which have been manufactured to operate at any European supply voltage in the range 230 V \pm 6%, should have no problem with the optimised voltage. Nevertheless, should any items experience difficulties, they can be connected to one of the UPS units, which have deliberately been set to output 240 V. This is because the transmitters were not able to operate stably when the output was set to 230 V.

3c) Telecommunications

Both the telephone and internet connections to the site were lost for just over 24 hours, starting at around 09:30 UT on 9th November 2010. The cause of the problem is not known.

DPW and LD have reported that internet speeds appear to have been lower than expected over the past few months. When DAH spoke to Eclipse, the service provider, on 1st February 2011, he found out that this was the result of the site's modems using out-of-date login details. It transpires that Eclipse had created new accounts in March 2008 after BT had caused the existing internet connections to be cancelled (see minutes of the 41st meeting for further details). However, the site's modems successfully logged back in using the old account details when internet connectivity was re-established 5 days later. Consequently DAH had never realised that anything might have changed. Eclipse confirmed that this would explain the recently-experienced problems. However, they were amazed that the old account details were still providing any connectivity. DPW successfully switched over to the new account details

for the Manchester network on 9th February 2011. Despite making repeated attempts, DAH was unable to change the settings on the modem for the NERC network. DPW has subsequently reported transfer speeds of 600 kbit/s for uploads and 3 Mbit/s for downloads on the Manchester network but only 100 kbit/s and 200 kbit/s, respectively, on the NERC network.

3d) Miscellaneous

The padlock for the main site gate has been changed to a high-security, combination model in January 2011. This is primarily for the purpose of restricting the number of people who have independent access to the site. Anyone who feels that they need such access should speak to DAH.

The winter of 2010/2011 was another exceptionally cold one. Between 25th November and 26th December 2010, daily minimum site temperatures were commonly between -5 and -10°C. DPW had drained the water tank in the attic at the beginning of the cold spell and so had prevented the possibility of pipes bursting. The bolts and the padlock on the main gate tended to freeze up over night, which made opening the gate rather problematic. As described in the next section, the extreme cold appears to have led to a few minor problems with the MST Radar and the laser ceilometer.

A recent aeronautical project, which made use of MST radar wind data, culminated in flight trials being undertaken to test improved airport approach procedures. The procedures were found to reduce both aircraft noise and fuel burn. Understandably, NERC showed interest in this project and published an article about it on their "Planet Earth" website - <http://planetearth.nerc.ac.uk/news/story.aspx?id=820>. The story was subsequently picked up for an article in NERC's Science Impacts Database - <http://sid.nerc.ac.uk>. This contains short case studies that demonstrate where NERC-funded research has had actual or potential social, economic, policy or practical impacts. The second article is due for publication later in the year.

In October 2010, Jooney Woodward, a documentary photographer who currently specialises in Welsh landscapes, visited the site. She had initially come across the MST radar antenna array by chance and thought that it would make a striking subject for a photograph. Some of Jooney's work can be seen at <http://www.jooneywoodward.co.uk/>.

It was reported at the last meeting that Honey Bees had taken up residence in the wooden site shed during the summer of 2010. The bees have not been sighted for several months and so it seems likely that they have vacated the premises.

3e) Changes to NERC's data access conditions

GAP reported that NERC had introduced a new data policy in January 2011 - see <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/research/sites/data/policy.asp>. From now on, any data acquired through NERC funding must be made publicly available within 2 years of acquisition. The embargo period is designed to allow the scientists responsible for collecting the data to have an exclusive chance to analyse them. Thereafter anyone can use the data for any purpose. The BADC will only be able to track usage through IP addresses. GV approved of this change with regard to the MSTRF dataset but thought that the data should be made immediately accessible rather than waiting for 2 years.

4. NERC Instrument Report

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

LD cleaned out the tipping bucket rain gauge on the morning of 29th June 2010. It had become blocked with gunge.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors (Frongoch)

There have been no problems with this instrument over the past 6 months.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

There have been a number of occasions when the tipping bucket rain gauge detected precipitation but the WXT510 did not: on 1st, 13th, 14th, 20th and 21st July 2010. Although it is possible that some of this rain was too light to be detected by the piezo-electric sensor, it was sufficiently heavy at other times to suggest an instrument problem. Consequently the WXT510 was power cycled on the morning of 27th July 2010. DAH did not want to take this step earlier, otherwise it would not have been clear whether the wrong sort of rain or an instrument problem was to blame. Although the WXT510 generated rain messages during a moderately intense precipitation event on the morning of 17th August 2010, the rates were lower than those measured by the tipping bucket rain gauge by at least an order of magnitude. A similar problem occurred on 20th August 2010.

No WXT510 data were recorded between 1st and 6th December 2010. This was the result of DAH forgetting to restart the acquisition software after the acquisition PC "augustus" was powered down to allow PAT to be carried out.

No data were recorded for about an hour around the middle of the day on both 19th and 20th January 2011. The cause of these gaps is not known.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

The absolute date-time stamps produced by the LD40's internal clock are known to be unreliable. The values of the date fields do not conform to the standard calendar system and the time tends to drift by several minutes over the course of months. DAH seldom attempts to reset the clock but relies on software corrections when producing daily files. He had to introduce a new correction on 3rd August 2010 after the internal clock was passively reset by a break in the electricity supply on the previous day (see section 3b).

There is a gap in the recorded data for several hours on 29th November 2010 and for just under an hour on 1st December 2010. The cause is unknown, although it is likely to have been the result of the extreme cold. Although data messages were recorded between 12:30 UT on 20th December 2010 and 15:00 UT the following day, the LD40 was not transmitting laser pulses. The error codes ("00050004") indicate: "*Test laser failure. Error. No more measurements possible*". This problem last occurred during the very cold weather of January 2010.

4e) Sky camera

There is a gap in the recorded images between 10:00 and 10:58 UT on 1st December 2010. The acquisition PC "claudius" had to be powered down to allow PAT to be carried out.

4f) MST Radar

The Met Office's monthly model-comparison statistics do not suggest any long-term problems with data quality over the past 6 months.

As usual, non-contaminating interference (i.e. which was successfully filtered out by the signal processing) was seen on a number of occasions: on 21st, 22nd, 24th and 26th June 2010, 5th and 18th July, 3rd and 28th August, and 7th December. The non-contaminating interference which was seen on 28th and 29th November 2010, and on 3rd December, appears to have been somehow caused by the extreme cold. Interference which caused some mild contamination of the wind profile data was seen on just 3 occasions: on 6th July 2010, and on 8th and 9th December 2010.

The radial-continuity test within the signal processing scheme is typically highly-effective at avoiding

ground clutter signals. However, large values of the (diagnostic) complementary beam velocity variability factor, at an altitude of around 6.5 km, suggest that this was not the case for at least one of the (6°) off-vertical beams on the afternoon of 6th September 2010. Since such large values cause the corresponding horizontal wind measurements to be flagged as being unreliable, this did not ultimately lead to any contamination of the wind-profile data. They are, however, of signal processing interest.

The beam steering unit became stuck in a single off-vertical direction between 23:25 and 23:55 UT on 17th September 2010. Consequently the wind-profile data for this period are invalid, despite having been flagged as reliable. The problem recurred at 17:00 UT the following day, a Saturday, and so was not spotted until first thing on the following Monday morning (20th September). DAH blocked the data feed to the Met Office shortly after 07:00 UT and LD was able to visit the later the same morning. He traced the cause of the fault to a loose circuit board and normal operations were resumed by 11:15 UT.

The beam steering unit again became stuck in a single off-vertical direction on 30th September 2010. LD happened to spot the problem early on from the online quick-look plot and so was able to visit the site shortly afterwards. He was able to isolate the cause of the problem to Quad number 8 by watching the way in which the patterns change on the beam steering unit indicator panel. He disconnected the control cable for Quad number 8 from the beam steering unit and normal operations were resumed within three hours of the problem first occurring.

Met Office monthly model-comparison statistics are useful for highlighting long term problems with data quality, e.g. when the new radar control and data acquisition system introduced a range gating error (see minutes of the 41st meeting for further details). However, they are of no use for rapidly identifying short term problems such as those described above. DAH presented daily statistics from the European E-WINPROF programme which clearly highlight the first beam steering unit problem. Data quality for each day is summarised by a number of single-valued parameters. For one of these, the root mean square of wind mean vector difference, there is a target maximum permissible value of 5.0 m s^{-1} . The values for most of September 2010 varied between 2.9 and 5.6 m s^{-1} . However, they jumped to 30.7, 22.5 and 11.6 m s^{-1} for the 18th, 19th and 20th when the beam steering unit had become stuck. It's not clear whether the value of 25.6 m s^{-1} for 26th September is correct as the quick-look plots do not suggest any problems with the radar.

Finally, a gradual reduction in useful radar altitude coverage on 10th November 2010 turned out to be caused by a signal processing problem rather than a hardware one. The time continuity algorithm should only compare wind profiles which have been made within one hour of each other. A blockage in the signal processing data flow (possibly a result of the loss of internet connection on the previous day - see section 3c) meant that wind-profiles from the previous day were also being used. Once DAH had recognised that the problem looked similar to one seen in early April 2007 (see minutes of the 39th meeting for further details), he was quickly able to resolve it.

DK emphasised the importance of not sending bad data to the Met Office. Consequently it is necessary to develop algorithms for identifying hardware problems which can give rise to invalid data which will pass self-consistency quality control checks.

ACTION ITEM 46.4.1 DK to set up a working group for developing quality control algorithms for wind-profiling radars.

NEW

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - EGN

The FGAM BLWP has been in operation at Cardington since April 2010. It has recently been operated alongside a WINDCUBE Doppler lidar, manufactured by Leosphere, and a Halo Photonics Doppler lidar for intercomparison purposes.

All of the raw data from 2002 are now archived on the BADC. BUFR data have been sent to the Met Office for CWINDE.

The BLWP will return to Capel Dewi in the autumn of 2011. However, during June, it will first return to Degreane for an upgrade. It is showing signs of rust after being located at the Weyborne coastal station and the paint is peeling off the antennas. These have an anticipated lifetime of 10-15 years and the instrument is now 8 years old.

DK reported that the Met Office were in a similar position with their Vaisala-manufactured BLWPs. These are due for a midlife upgrade within the next couple of years. However, there is some uncertainty with regard to the 1290 MHz operating frequency, which lies within one of the bands to be used by the European Galileo Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS). At present there are only 2 Galileo satellites in operation. However, there will eventually be 24 of them. Moreover, Russian and Chinese GNSSs may make adjacent frequency bands unavailable. There is perhaps potential to use 1260 MHz, which lies between the European and Russian systems. If this was the case, the existing Vaisala antennas could continue to be used. However, they are unsuitable for operations at a higher frequency. GV pointed out that several years ago the FGAM instrument had taken part in tests to evaluate the potential impact of Galileo operations on BLWPs. These had concluded that there would be little impact. No problems have yet been encountered as a result of the 2 test Galileo satellites.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.1 EGN to send DK a copy of the report on the potential impact of Galileo operations on BLWPs.

NEW

5b) University of Manchester static instruments - GV

The Elight lidar was configured for making volcanic ash observations during the spring of 2010. It has now switched back to making BL observations. The water vapour lidar is operational, but has not been used much recently. DPW is in the process of trying to improve the power on the ozone lidar.

GV additionally reported that one of his Manchester colleagues had been contacted by a company which operates a network of lightning detectors across Europe. They were looking to install a new one in the British Isles and GV had thought that the MSTRF site would make a good potential location.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

Jon Jones, who was not at the meeting, had reported to DAH that he needs to visit the MSTRF site in order to investigate the GPS receiver. Incorrect dates and times are being recorded in the data files and he cannot diagnose the fault remotely. DAH read out the following report on Jon's behalf.

In the UK around 150 GPS sites are run on a continual, operational basis. Whilst the majority of the sites are owned by 3rd parties (Ordnance Survey GB for example) the Met Office owns and operates 12 GPS stations sending hourly raw GPS data for processing. Also, an additional 120 or so European sites are included in the processing making the total processed around 250 sites for any one hour. The data is processed using the Bernese v5.0 GPS processing software and Zenith Total Delay (ZTD) estimates are generated at 15 minute intervals (for the previous hour) and this data is operationally assimilated into the UK4 and NAE models. The ZTD is also converted to Integrated Water Vapour (IWV) if surface parameters are known, and this data is presented to the forecasters as 2D IWV plots - see

<http://egvap.dmi.dk> and click on "Products" at the top right.

As well as operational use, the data is also an excellent benchmark for validation of other remote sensing instruments as well as for composite observing projects such as the Met Office Future Upper-Air Network Development project.

DK reported that the Met Office was purchasing 14 new CHM 15k Laser Cloud Base Recorders (LCBRs) from Jenoptik. These have the option to use a second polarimetric channel, which would be useful for identifying volcanic ash. DK was interested in operating one at the MSTRF site. Since these instruments operate at 1064 nm, they would not cause problems for the existing Vaisala LD40, which operates at 855 nm. Potentially the data from all 14 new instruments could be made available through the BADC.

ACTION ITEM 46.5.2 DAH and DK to investigate the possibility of operating one of the Met Office's new Jenoptik LCBRs at the MSTRF site.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik LCBRs on the BADC.

NEW

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) COST Action ES0702: boundary-layer depth estimates - EGN and CG

The aim of this work is to evaluate the the potential of two different algorithms for determining BL depth from BLWP data.

One algorithm, which was developed by NOAA for use with BLWPs in Colorado, relies on fuzzy logic. It considers the signal-to-noise ratio, the vertical beam spectral width, and the variance of vertical velocity. It makes use of reality checks based on the time of day and on the latitude and longitude at which the observations were made. The algorithm is a standard component of Vaisala BLWP processing software. The second algorithm, which considers similar BLWP signal parameters, was developed by EGN based on the work by Angevine.

It was hoped to test the algorithms on data both from the FGAM BLWP, which was manufactured by Degreane and operated (for the test period) at Cardington, and from one of the Met Office's BLWPs, which was manufactured by Vaisala and operated at Wattisham. However, owing to data incompatibilities, it was difficult to process the Degreane data using the Vaisala software. The study focused on 5-beam observations (the Met Office typically use 4-beam observations for operational profiling) made by the Vaisala/Wattisham BLWP between May and October 2010 in the low-altitude coverage mode (data from the high-altitude coverage mode were found to be too coarse). When there was a clearly-defined BL top (only seen on 15 days), both algorithms performed comparably well. When a residual layer was present (on a further 14 days), both algorithms tended to lock on to this. They similarly tended to lock on to the higher layer when two potential layers were present.

DK pointed out that there was no single, clear definition of BL height within the numerical weather prediction community. It had become clear to him, in investigating how the BLWP data might be best assimilated, that observations would need to be tailored towards the end needs - and that there might be several different sets of needs.

Special observations have also been made using the Met Office's Degreane-manufactured BLWP at Chilbolton. It was necessary to hack the software in order to extract the vertical velocity from every

available vertical beam dwell. These can be compared with data from the Halo Doppler lidar. DK pointed out that differences might be expected owing to the fact that the BLWP has a broad beam whereas the lidar makes a spot-like observation. JP pointed out that the lidar would be sampling smaller scales within the turbulence spectrum than the radar.

6b) Radars and turbulence - CFL

CFL has compared MST radar and FGAM BLWP data with simultaneous aircraft and radiosonde data. Vertical-beam power-spectrum radar signals associated with turbulence are expected to be Gaussian in shape. However, this is often far from being true. Averaging the spectra over 5 and 20 minutes tends to progressively improve the approximation. It is first necessary to shift the peaks of the signals to a common Doppler velocity, since the mean vertical velocity can vary significantly over such periods. Failure to do this will lead to an unwanted increase in the spectral width, from which the turbulence intensity is derived.

Observed spectral widths tend to be dominated by the beam-broadening component, which is proportional to both the horizontal wind speed and the radar's beam width. However, in the existing literature, it is seldom clear which definitions of spectral width and beam width have been used. This leads to a low confidence in the derived values of turbulence intensity. The second moment method of spectral width calculation gives a half-width at 1 standard deviation from the mean Doppler velocity. The appropriate beam width to use for beam-broadening correction is the two-way half-width at one standard deviation. The observed widths can be overestimated for a number of reasons. For example, they never drop below a finite value, equivalent to 1 - 2 velocity bin widths, even for wind speeds close to zero. Moreover, the tails of a signal have a disproportionately large effect on increasing the measured widths by the second moment method. This is less significant if Gaussian fitting is used.

There are also problems with interpreting the aircraft data. For example, the power spectrum of horizontal winds is expected to show a $-5/3$ slope. However, it can be steeper than this, at the top of the BL for example. Moreover, at some altitudes, considerably more power has been seen at the highest frequencies (corresponding to horizontal scale sizes of < 1 km) of the vertical velocity spectrum than is expected.

6c) THAW temperature structures - DJH

This work is based on a 2009 aircraft observation campaign to look at "temperature, humidity, and winds" (THAW). The focus is on the fine-scale temperature structure in the vicinity of the tropopause in an attempt to show that it is dominated by laminar "sheets" rather than turbulent irregularities. At this stage the observed temperature structures are being used to model the expected MST radar return power. The ultimate aim is to be able to derive the temperature structure from the MST radar data.

Attention is focused on potential rather than regular temperature in order to avoid the effects of any gravity wave perturbations. The data are high-pass filtered in order to remove the effects of aircraft motions. It appears that the temperature structure is dominated by multiple small-magnitude temperature steps rather than a few large-magnitude ones. The winds were strong on the day when the aircraft flew spiral patterns, and so it is not possible to directly compare data from one level flight section with those from the next. There may also be some contamination of the high-pass filtered data from the fact that it was difficult to fly at constant ascent rate. GV pointed out that spiral legs cannot be flown by auto-pilot and that it is difficult to fly the plane at a steady vertical rate of 500 foot per minute.

DJH is currently looking at the aircraft-measured winds in order to rule out the possibility of turbulence. He is making use of radar aspect sensitivity data in order to highlight sheet structures. He is feeding the observational data into an atmospheric structure model.

6d) Plans for DIAMET and TROSIAD - GV

The Diabatic Influences on Mesoscale Structures in Extra-Tropical Storms (DIAMET) project is funded under the NERC Storms Risk Mitigation programme. It is being lead by NCAS with National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO) and Met Office involvement. In simplistic terms, rainfall creates Potential Vorticity (PV) and PV affects the dynamics of storms. Although it is known how this works at the synoptic scale, it's not clear whether the mesoscale features produced by models are real or not.

Field campaigns involving the FAAM aircraft will take place during autumn 2011 and summer 2012. One of the work packages is aimed at improving the modelling of convective processes. It will focus on ice microphysics and air-sea interaction parameterisations. A second work package will focus on ensemble modelling. Measurement campaigns will be based around the FAAM aircraft. They will follow up on the T-NAWDEX campaign, which involved the deployment of dropsondes as the aircraft flew through a front. Over land, lots of precipitation was found where it wasn't modelled to be. There was evidence of banding in the meridional velocities observed by the MST radar on 13th November 2009, but curiously not in the zonal velocities. GV pointed out the version-3 quality control erred on the side of caution and that better coverage could be obtained by creative use of the low-level reliability information.

There is potential for flights to be made on weekdays between 14th and 30th September 2011 from Cranfield and on any day between 23rd November and 8th December 2011 from Exeter. Exact dates remain to be confirmed for a July/August 2012 phase. The aircraft will start off at high levels before descending to altitudes characterised by a temperature of around -10°C , at which ice microphysics is important. Mixed-phase clouds are currently difficult to model. The MST radar will support this campaign and the FGAM BLWP will return to Capel Dewi,

The aims of TROSIAD, which is funded through a standard NERC grant, are different to those of DIAMET but are complementary. It will focus on the effects of stratospheric intrusions on convection. As well as making use of the MST radar data archive, it will have a dedicated campaign phase. This will overlap with the DIAMET period but will be more extensive in order to ensure that the appropriate conditions are encountered. It will run between 12th September and 16th December 2011 in the first instance and during July and August 2012 in the second. GV did not want to go ahead with this until the MST radar has been renovated as the altitude coverage is not currently good enough.

DK offered GV data from the Met Office wind-profilers in support of the DIAMET campaign. However, he (DK) said that a mechanism needs to be put in place in order to make the data more-rapidly available. GAP pointed out that Met Office BLWP data were available through the BADC within 6 hours - though this is still too slow for the purposes of the campaign. CG pointed out that wind-profile data were available through the CWINDE website within an hour. GV clarified that he primarily needs rapid access to rainfall radar data.

6e) Discussion of lidar technologies - DK

There are two specific areas for which lidar observations could have a strong impact for internal Met Office data users. The first is in the measurement of BL humidity, which is extremely important for numerical weather prediction. At present this is only measured by radiosondes and so it is limited to twice daily soundings at 4 locations across the UK. In principle the combination of a radiometer and a BLWP could be used, although the altitude resolution would probably be too low. A Raman lidar could be used during the daytime, but a water vapour lidar would be far more appropriate. The second area of interest is in volcanic ash. Although the chances of an ash cloud spreading over the British Isles within the next few years are thought to be small, it would be prudent to have an observation network in place which is capable of detecting it.

Any instruments to be used within the Met Office's observational network must be robust and designed for unmanned operations. DK expects any lidars to be of a lower specification than the ones used for

research. JLA reported that she is interested in experimenting with a laser approximately 1/10th as powerful as the current one in the Chilbolton lidar. She hopes that this would make the system more reliable and robust. It would need to be capable of overcoming the solar background levels. GV suggested that narrower band lasers might help. One of the big challenges is to be able to stabilise the temperature of the room in which the laser is operated. The receiver side is less critical.

DK reported that the Met Office are in the process of deploying their new Jenoptik LCBRs across the British Isles. These instruments are significantly more powerful than the existing LCBRs in the Met Office's network. They are capable of detecting volcanic ash at altitudes of up to 4.5 km, rather than 2.0 km. Nevertheless, they're not as powerful as research lidars, which will still be of key importance in the case of another volcanic ash episode. GV and JLA pointed out that there needed to be clearer and more-effective methods of exchanging data in the case of a repeat event. Everything was done on an *ad hoc* basis during the spring of 2010. DK reported that all data would need to be made available using a common netCDF-based format, which has yet to be defined. He also reported that Owen Cox (at the Met Office) had developed a powerful plotting tool for LCBR data and that this could probably be extended to deal with volcanic ash data. It was noted that the WMO has set up a global aerosol watch sub-programme, although progress in this area was rather slow.

DK would like to set up regular meetings, possibly as part of the MSTRF meetings, for the discussion of lidar observations and developments. It was pointed out that lidar expertise could be found at the Universities of Manchester, Leeds, Oxford, and (possibly) Edinburgh and at the Chilbolton and (possibly) Herstmonceux facilities.

ACTION ITEM 46.6.1 DK to set up a working group for those with expertise in lidar operations.

NEW

7. Any Other Business

It was pointed out that the Royal Met Soc conference was taking place in Exeter during the final week of June 2011 and that the NCAS Staff Meeting was taking place on 6-7 July. The date for the next Experimenters' meeting was set for Tuesday 5th July 2011.